

Fundamental mode instability in few mode optical fiber

M. Ferraro^{1,*}, W.A. Gemechu², S. Boni², F. Mangini², A. Ciorra², Y. Sun^{2,3},
K. Stefańska², M. Gervaziev^{4,5}, D. Kharenko^{4,5}, S. Babin^{4,5}, V. Couderc⁶, S. Wabnitz²

¹Department of Physics, University of Calabria, Via P. Bucci, Rende 87036, Italy

²DIET, Sapienza University of Rome, Via Eudossiana 18, 00184 Rome, Italy

³Service OPERA-Photonique, Université libre de Bruxelles, 50 Ave. F. D. Roosevelt, B-1050 Brussels, Belgium

⁴Novosibirsk State University, Pirogova 1, Novosibirsk 630090, Russia

⁵Institute of Automation and Electrometry, SB RAS, Novosibirsk 630090, Russia,

⁶Université de Limoges, XLIM UMR CNRS 7252, 123 Avenue A. Thomas, 87060, Limoges, France

*mario.ferraro92@unical.it

Abstract: We experimentally observe a nonlinear instability of a femtosecond pulse carried by the fundamental mode of a few-mode optical fiber, leading to the preferential population of the higher-order modes. © 2025 The Author(s)

Nonlinear optical effects in multimode optical fibers have attracted considerable research attention in the past ten years, both for their application impact in developing novel high energy laser sources, and for the fundamental interest in the study of complex physical systems [1, 2]. In this context, an intriguing nonlinear effect that is inherent to highly multimode fibers is beam self-cleaning, whereby a speckled beam transforms into a bell-shaped beam dominated by the fundamental mode of the fiber, as the input power is increased above a certain threshold value [3]. On the other hand, there is considerable interest in studying nonlinear effects in few-mode fibers, specifically in the context of mode-division multiplexed fiber transmissions. Nonlinear effects such as modal four-wave mixing have been studied in few-mode fibers for a long time. However, relatively little attention has been paid so far to the occurrence of nonlinear beam-reshaping effects.

In this work, we reveal the presence of a so far unnoticed modal instability in few-mode fibers, whereby a femtosecond laser beam coupled to the fiber's fundamental mode loses its spatial stability at high peak powers. As a result, the fundamental beam is fully depleted and its energy is stably transferred to the higher-order modes of the fiber. The resulting multimode beam pattern turns out to be very stable upon any external fiber perturbations such as bending and squeezing. In this respect, the observed nonlinear mode reshaping effect has a strong similarity with the beam self-cleaning, but it acts in a reverse manner, as far as the resulting mode power distribution is concerned. The fundamental mode instability discussed here has analogies with a similar type of instability and resulting transfer of energy into the higher-order modes which is activated by self-focusing in hollow-core fibers [4].

Fig. 1. Experimental output near-field intensity at low (a) and high (b) powers, respectively.

In our experiments, we used a femtosecond pulse laser system: the laser beam was injected at the center of a standard SMF-28 optical fiber operated in the normal dispersion regime and below cutoff so that it supported the propagation of up to five guided modes. Figure 1 compares the experimental output beam intensity profile at low powers (left) with the beam profile observed at peak powers of the order of 100 kW. As can be seen, in linear propagation conditions the beam has a bell-shaped intensity profile close to that of the fundamental mode. Whereas at high powers a two-lobes multimode beam is formed.

We have numerically simulated pulse propagation in the few-mode fiber with the help of the generalized multimode coupled nonlinear Schrödinger equations, including self-steepening and Raman scattering, and obtained a good qualitative agreement (see Figure 2).

Fig. 2. Simulated output near-field intensity at low (a) and high (b) powers, respectively.

Fig. 3. Mode power distribution at the fiber output in the linear regime (a) and in the highly nonlinear regime (b); insets show the output near field and its reconstruction, respectively.

In order to analyze the change in the output mode power distribution, the beam emerging from the fiber was directed onto a spatial light modulator by combining two lenses. The near-field profile was subsequently imaged after being reflected from a flip mirror by using a CCD camera. The optical devices in the output of the fiber enabled us to perform a holographic mode decomposition as in Ref. [5]. As shown in Figure 3, our mode-decomposition permitted to reveal that, while at low powers the beam is dominated by the fundamental mode, at high powers the fundamental mode is virtually fully depleted and the distribution is dominated by the highest-order modes (here the modes are ordered according to their propagation constant).

In conclusion, we have revealed the presence of nonlinear modal instability in solid-core few-mode optical fibers, leading to the full depletion of the fundamental mode in favor of modes of the highest order. We anticipate that these results may have an important impact on the design and operation of multimode optical fiber systems and devices.

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